

Effects of Peer Assessment Technique on Students' Academic Achievement and Interest in Mensuration in Upper Basic Schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria

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Abstract *The study examined effects of peer-assessment technique on students' academic achievement and interest in Mathematics in Upper Basic Schools II in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The study adopted a Quasi Experimental Research Design and used the pretest – posttest non-randomized control group design. The area covered by this study is Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State. This education zone consists of Enugu East, Enugu North and Isi-uzo Local Government Areas of Enugu State. The population of the study consisted of all the Upper Basic School Two (UBSII) students in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State numbering 5,628 (male = 2,492 and female =3,136). A sample of 120 Upper Basic School II (UBSII) students (58 males and 62 females) was used for the study. The researcher used a multi-stage sampling technique to draw the sample for the study. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS) were used to collect data for the study. The data was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The result revealed that peer assessment, which is a method of assessment whereby learners are allowed to assess their peers and give feedback based on a given rule had significant effect on students' academic achievements and interest in mathematics. The study also revealed that peer assessment method is significant in enhancing students' academic achievement in mathematics. The study further indicated that peer assessment in enhancing male and female students' interest in mathematics does not differ significantly. Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that when Peer Assessment is properly used by teachers, the academic performance and achievement of the students will not only improve but it can also enable the students to better understand and develop keen interest in the contents of the subject. Proper understanding and interest in the contents of the subject will enable the students not only to perform better but enhance academic achievement. The study recommended that peer assessment strategy should be used by teachers in the teaching and assessment of student in mathematics.*

Keywords: *Peer Assessment, Academic Achievement, Student Interest, Mensuration, Mathematics Education*

Background to the Study

Mensuration, a fundamental concept in mathematics, involves measuring lengths, areas, and volumes of shapes and objects. Its importance extends beyond the classroom to fields like architecture, engineering, and everyday problem-solving (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, 2014). However, despite its relevance, students'

achievements in mensuration are discouraging. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's report (2021) highlighted that many students fail to attempt or properly solve mensuration questions, reflecting broader struggles with mathematics (Lubienski, 2019; Sullivan, 2013).

In Enugu State, Nigeria, upper basic school students face persistent difficulties in understanding and applying mensuration concepts (Uzoegwu, 2015). Educators and stakeholders emphasize exploring innovative teaching and assessment methods to improve outcomes. Among these methods, peer assessment has emerged as a promising technique, encouraging critical thinking, communication skills, and collaborative learning (Tillema, 2014; Van den Berg, 2015). However, further research is needed to evaluate its effectiveness in enhancing students' interest and achievement in mensuration.

Academic achievement reflects students' intellectual performance in a subject and is often measured through tests (Ali & Kalu, 2011). Mathematics, regarded as a foundation for scientific and technological advancement, is prioritized in Nigeria's educational policies (Stafford, 2013). It is a core subject at all levels, and a credit in mathematics is mandatory for admission to tertiary institutions.

Despite its significance, students often achieve poor results. For instance, only 27.29% of students earned credit passes in mathematics during the 2005 National Examination Council (NECO) exams, with fluctuations in subsequent years (Nworgu, 2016). The WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2021) similarly revealed inconsistent performance trends, with a significant portion of students failing to credit mathematics. Researchers like Agwagah (as cited in Ugwuanyi, 2019) and Akiri and Nkechi (2019) attribute poor outcomes to ineffective teaching methods, lack of motivation, and inadequate classroom interactions.

Students perceive mensuration as difficult and uninteresting due to its abstract nature. Traditional teaching methods, predominantly teacher-led assessments, have proven insufficient in addressing these challenges. These methods often exclude students from the assessment process, limiting opportunities for peer learning and feedback.

Peer assessment, where students evaluate each other's work based on set criteria, offers an alternative. This technique promotes engagement, critical analysis, and ownership of the learning process, potentially improving interest and performance (Race, 2011). Despite its benefits, peer assessment is underutilized in mathematics education, partly due to teachers' lack of awareness about its effectiveness.

Assessment measures the extent of behavioral changes and learning outcomes in students. It provides critical feedback for teachers to guide and motivate students (Rodriguez, 2014). Traditional assessments, where teachers grade assignments and tests, allow for one-on-one consultations with weaker students but are time-intensive and less interactive.

In contrast, peer assessment involves students in the evaluation process, fostering collaboration and immediate feedback. It has been shown to enhance interest, reduce teachers' workload, and develop students' analytical skills (Saddler & Good, 2016).

Interest, defined as the motivation to engage with a subject or activity, plays a significant role in learning (Bhatia, 2013). It can be influenced by factors like reinforcement, learning experiences, and rewards (Eke, 2016). Students with high interest in a subject tend to concentrate better and achieve higher outcomes (Biehler & Snowman, 2017). In mathematics, cultivating interest is crucial to overcoming students' negative perceptions. Studies show that interactive strategies, such as peer assessment, can boost interest by creating a supportive learning environment (Njoku, 2013).

The influence of gender on academic achievement in mathematics remains inconclusive. While some studies suggest that males and females process information differently, others find no significant differences (Orsmond, 2015; Race, 2011). Sociocultural factors and biological differences may contribute to variations in performance (Davies & Hersh, 2012).

Given these debates, it is essential to examine whether gender affects students' interest and achievement in mensuration. Peer assessment aligns with calls for student-centered teaching approaches. By involving students in evaluating each other's work, it can address traditional assessment's limitations and foster a deeper understanding of mensuration. This study aims to investigate whether peer assessment improves interest and academic achievement in mensuration among upper basic school students in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the importance of mensuration in mathematics, students in upper basic schools in Enugu state continued to show poor academic achievement and lack of interest in the subject. Traditional teaching methods and summative assessments may not be adequately preparing students for challenges of mensuration, leading to a gap in their understanding and application of mathematical concepts. The use of peer assessment techniques has been shown to improve academic achievement and interest in mathematics in other contexts but its effectiveness in upper basic schools in Enugu state remains unknown. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the effects of peer assessment techniques on students' academic achievement and interest in mensuration in upper basic schools in Enugu state with a view to identifying strategies to improve teaching and learning mathematics in Enugu state.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the effects of Peer-Assessment technique on Students' Interest and Academic Achievement in mensuration in Upper Basic II Schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

- i) the mean achievement scores of students exposed to peer assessment technique in mensuration in the experimental group and control group in both pretest and posttest.
- ii) the mean interest scores of students do taught Mensuration as a topic in Mathematics using peer assessment technique in the experimental group and control group in both pretest and posttest

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students exposed to Mensuration using peer assessment technique in the experimental group and the control group in both pretest and posttest?
2. What are the mean interest scores of students do taught Mensuration using peer assessment technique in the experimental group and the control group in both pretest and posttest?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 levels of significances:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of upper Basic two school students exposed to Mensuration as a topic in Mathematics using peer assessment technique in experimental and control group the pretest and posttest test scores of students in the peer assessment group (experimental group) and control group in Enugu Education Zone in Enugu State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of upper Basic two school students taught Mensuration as a topic in Mathematics using peer assessment technique in experimental and control group the pretest and posttest test scores of students in the peer assessment group (experimental group) and control group in Enugu Education Zone in Enugu State.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Mathematics.

Mathematics is a fundamental and ancient discipline central to human thought and innovation. Perez-Bergquist (2012) characterized it as a unique field that transcends conventional classifications like language, science, or art, while incorporating elements of all three. Mathematics enables us to decode the patterns and structures underlying the world around us. Mitchner (2013) elaborated that modern mathematics extends beyond basic arithmetic and geometry to include data analysis, measurements, and complex modeling of phenomena in natural and social sciences. It is a science of abstract entities such as numbers, forms, and algorithms, relying on logic as its standard of truth while utilizing observation and experimentation as tools for discovery.

The discipline also offers distinctive models of thought—abstraction, optimization, and logical analysis—that are invaluable in addressing modern challenges (Hanna & Dettmer, 2014). Mathematics empowers critical thinking, the detection of biases, risk assessment, and the suggestion of alternatives, equipping individuals to navigate an information-rich world.

The evolution of mathematics witnessed significant milestones in the late 19th and early 20th centuries with the advent of abstraction and axiomatic frameworks. These advancements led to the formulation of powerful theories in algebra, topology, and applied mathematics (Rodriguez, 2014). The integration of mathematical principles into scientific exploration, particularly during the Second World War, further accelerated its development and practical applications. Today, mathematics is indispensable across disciplines such as engineering, medicine, and the social sciences, while pure mathematics continues to inspire theoretical and practical innovations (Cowan, 2015).

Student Interest in Mathematics

Interest plays a pivotal role in students' engagement and success in mathematics. Bhatia (2013) defined interest as a motivational force that fosters attention and enthusiasm toward learning activities. It develops through positive reinforcement, learning experiences, and instructional approaches (Njoku, 2013). Students are drawn to mathematics when teaching methods are varied, practical applications are emphasized, and instructional materials are effectively utilized.

Balogun (2015) emphasized the role of dynamic teaching techniques, such as using mathematical games and set induction strategies, to stimulate curiosity and sustain students' interest. Peer-assessment methods also contribute to building engagement by actively involving students in evaluating and reflecting on their work. The cultivation of interest is crucial, as it directly influences academic performance, making it a cornerstone of successful mathematical instruction.

Peer Assessment in Mathematics

Peer assessment is an instructional strategy where students evaluate their peers' work based on established criteria, facilitating active participation and deeper learning. Lutze-Mann (2014) defined peer assessment as a tool for developing critical thinking, self-awareness, and reflective practices. By engaging in this process, students enhance their understanding of assessment criteria and improve their ability to evaluate their own work.

The benefits of peer assessment include fostering higher-order cognitive skills, such as analysis, evaluation, and synthesis (Topping et al., 2017). It shifts some responsibility for learning onto students, promoting ownership and engagement while encouraging deeper comprehension over surface learning. Peer assessment can be used formatively to provide feedback or summatively to evaluate performance.

Despite its advantages, challenges such as fairness and the time required for peer review must be managed. Factors like students' individual biases or varying levels of competence can influence the fairness of evaluations (Lin et al., 2011). When effectively implemented, however, peer assessment not only supports academic achievement but also cultivates essential skills like teamwork, communication, and critical evaluation, making it a valuable technique in mathematics education.

Concept of Academic Achievement

Academic achievement refers to the educational outcomes achieved by individuals or institutions, reflecting the extent to which specific learning objectives have been met. It is most commonly assessed through examinations, continuous assessments, or a combination of both. Stiggins (2011) described academic achievement as encompassing not only excellence in core academic disciplines but also co-curricular activities such as sportsmanship, communication skills, punctuality, and engagement with arts and culture. These elements contribute to a holistic view of educational success, which extends beyond mere knowledge acquisition to include the development of life skills and values.

Cowan (2015) further defined academic achievement as the degree of competence or knowledge attained in school tasks, often measured through standardized tests and represented by grades or scores. Academic achievement also

includes changes in behavior and cognitive abilities resulting from structured learning experiences across various subjects (Hanna & Dettmer, 2014). In this study, academic achievement is analyzed in terms of its enhancement through peer-assessment techniques, with a focus on skill development in mathematics.

Concept of Gender and Academic Achievement

Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, attributes, and expectations associated with being male or female. These attributes evolve over time through socialization processes and influence individuals' relationships, responsibilities, and access to resources (Nnamani & Oyibe, 2016). Gender roles and expectations vary widely across cultures but often involve distinct opportunities and challenges for males and females. For instance, males are traditionally associated with boldness, competitiveness, and independence, while females are seen as nurturing, cooperative, and emotionally driven (Ezeudu & Obi, 2013; Sweeney, 2013).

Research into gender and academic achievement highlights persistent disparities shaped by biological, psychological, and sociocultural factors. Males are often found to excel in science and mathematics, potentially due to societal reinforcement of analytical and competitive traits (Ekeh, 2013). Conversely, females tend to demonstrate greater emotional motivation and enthusiasm for learning, which can lead to higher levels of engagement and achievement in certain contexts (Nasir & Masrur, 2015). Biological differences, such as brain structure and processing styles, also contribute to these patterns, as noted by Petrides and Furnham (2014).

The debate over gender differences in academic achievement remains active, with studies presenting mixed results. While some attribute differences to innate cognitive or neurological factors (Duckworth & Seligman, 2016), others emphasize the influence of societal expectations and educational practices. This study aims to examine how gender moderates the impact of peer-assessment techniques on academic achievement in mathematics among secondary school students in Enugu North Local Government Area. By addressing this variable, the research seeks to provide insights into the interplay between gender and pedagogical approaches in promoting equitable learning outcomes.

Theoretical Framework (Abridged and Slightly Expanded)

Constructivist Theory by Jean Piaget

Jean Piaget's constructivist theory, introduced in 1978, emphasizes that learners actively construct new knowledge and problem-solving strategies by building on prior experiences and current understanding. Asuai (2013) highlighted that constructivism centers on individuals creating their understanding of the world through experiences and reflection. This approach advocates active learning over passive reception, encouraging students to engage deeply with content rather than simply memorizing facts.

Constructivist teaching fosters learning through active participation and exploration. Students critique and re-evaluate their prior knowledge in a learning process marked by interpretation, articulation, and iterative refinement. Collaborative activities and peer feedback are essential, promoting deeper comprehension through

interaction. Analogously, just as one learns to ride a bicycle through practice rather than reading, constructivist learning emphasizes doing and practicing to achieve mastery.

Core Principles of Constructivist Teaching:

1. Promoting student autonomy and initiative.
2. Utilizing primary sources and interactive materials.
3. Incorporating cognitive processes like analysis and creation in planning.
4. Adapting lessons and strategies based on student feedback.
5. Encouraging inquiry and dialogue among students and teachers.
6. Supporting exploration, open-ended questioning, and critical thinking.
7. Allowing time for reflection, discussion, and hypothesis testing.

Strengths and Weaknesses:

Constructivist teaching supports hands-on learning, connecting classroom concepts to real-world applications. It values students' prior knowledge, fosters collaboration, and enhances social skills through group work. However, its limitations include the need for extensive teacher training, potential challenges in customizing lessons for diverse learners, and the reduced emphasis on standardized testing and grades.

Relevance to the Study:

Constructivism aligns with the study's goals by encouraging creativity, independence, and collaborative problem-solving in mathematics. It supports innovative teaching strategies, such as peer assessment, which empower students to actively engage and develop critical thinking skills.

Empirical Review

A study conducted by Oluwatomi and Moyosore (2014) investigated “The Effect of Peer – Assessment Strategy on Students’ Achievement in Senior Secondary School in Economics”. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of peer–assessment strategy on students’ achievement in senior secondary school in Economics. One hypothesis guided the study. The design of the study was quasi experimental design. The sample involved 90 Economics students in senior secondary school. The data for the study were collected using the constructed Economics Achievement Test (EAT) items; the data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The result of the study showed that there is a strong significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Economics students taught with Peer-Assessment Strategy laying emphasis on comparative judgment theory. This supported previous findings by Race (2011) who listed among the advantages of Peer-Assessment Strategy that it encourages deep learning by students, which leads to improvement in students’ performance than the other regular assessment practices. This study is different from the above because it involves 120 students of junior secondary schools students and the data were collected using the constructed Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) items.

Review from the study conducted by Nwadinigwe and Azuka-Obieke (2018) showed the impact of peer-assessment on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between peer-assessment and academic achievement among senior secondary school students. Two research hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental (pre-test/post-test control group) design was employed in the study. The sample consisted of 156 randomly selected participants from three senior secondary schools. The schools were randomly assigned to the two treatment conditions. The instruments for the study were Exploring Peer Assessment (EPA) two sections of 130-item instrument and a 60-item multiple choice objective test constructed by the researcher to measure achievement in Mathematics, English Language and Biology. The reliability coefficients of the instruments were 0.81 and 0.64. Hypotheses were tested using descriptive statistical method, analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. The study revealed that there is a positive relationship between peer-assessment and academic achievement such that allowing students to assess each other will lead to the enhancement of his/her academic achievement. Both studies used Quasi Experimental Design. Both studies used descriptive statistical method. ANCOVA was used to test its research hypotheses while the present study also made use of ANCOVA. Both studies used achievement test but the difference is that the reviewed study centered on students' academic achievement in Mathematics English Language and Biology but the present study centered only on Mathematics academic achievement; the reviewed study was done in Lagos State in Nigeria while the present study was carried out in Enugu, Nigeria. They both have a difference in the population size of 156 and 120 students respectively.

Investigation study of Festus (2019) showed the relationship between peer assessment and mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja-Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to determine whether there is a significant relationship between peer-assessment and academic achievement of students in Mathematics. Five research hypotheses guided the study. The instruments used for the correlation survey design study were the Peer Inventory for adolescents developed by Fani-Shing, Ying-Ming, Ching-Yua and Chia-An (2017) and Mathematics Achievement Test were used. The reliability coefficient was 0.79 while the Mathematics Achievement Test has reliability coefficient of 0.94. The population for the study was senior secondary school class 2 students in public schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The sample for the study was 1160 SS2 students in public schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria sampled by proportionate stratified sampling. Data were analyzed using mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. T-test was used to test the level of significance of the correlation coefficient. The result of the study showed that there was a significantly but low positive relationship between the peer-assessment of SS2 students and their academic achievement in Mathematics. However, unlike the reviewed literatures that was hinged on comparative judgment theory, the present study hinged on constructivists' theory by Jean Piaget to effects of peer-assessment technique on secondary school student's academic achievement in Mathematics in Upper Basic Two Secondary Schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

In reviewing studies relating to gender in peer assessment and academic achievement in Mathematics, Adigwe (2015) studied the influence of gender difference as it relates to peer-assessment on academic achievement of secondary school mathematics students. The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of gender difference as it relates to peer-assessment on academic achievement of secondary school mathematics students. Seven hypotheses guided the study. Ex post facto design was adopted; the population was mathematics secondary school students in Nsukka Education Zone. Stratified sampling technique was used to draw three urban and three rural schools from the three local government areas in the Education zone. The sample consisted of 310 students: 141 male students and 169 female students. Instruments for the study were a Mathematics solving test consisting of fifty multiple-choice items based on problem solving in Mathematics, and Mathematics Achievement Test. These tests were administered to all the subjects and were collected on the spot. 3x2x2 ANOVA and correlational analyses involving the achievement scores and the peer-assessment techniques were made. It was found that peer-assessment significantly influenced students' achievement, gender had no significant influence on the students' achievement in mathematics, there is no significant interaction influence of gender and peer-assessment on students' achievement. Adigwe's study was conducted in Nsukka education zone. However, the current study accessed the effects of peer-assessment technique on secondary school student's academic achievement in mathematics in upper basic two secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu state.

In the study carried out by Ogundokun and Adeyemo (2019) the comparative influence of peer assessment technique and teacher assessment technique on academic achievement of secondary school students was investigated. The purpose of the study was to investigate the comparative influence of peer assessment technique and teacher assessment technique on academic achievement of secondary school students. Five research hypotheses were employed to guide the study. The survey research involved 1563 secondary school students in Oyo state Nigeria (826 male and 737 female) as sample. The instrument for data collection were Peer Assessment and Teacher Assessment Inventory (PATAI) by Ashkanasy (2018), with Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.88, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation scale (IEMS) by Lepper, Corpus and Iyengar (2013), with Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.75, English language achievement test (EAT) and Mathematics achievement test (MAT), with Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.77. Descriptive statistics, Pearson's product moment correlation and hierarchical regression were used to analyze the data. The findings of the study showed that Teacher assessment influenced academic achievement of students more than peer assessment. The study was conducted in Oyo state, Nigeria and took a pore on Ashkanasy's Peer Assessment and Teacher Assessment Method (PATAM). This current study used Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS) and Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) to determine the effects of peer-assessment technique on secondary school student's academic achievement in mathematics in upper basic two secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu state.

Research Method

Design of the Study

This study adopted a Quasi Experimental Research Design and used the pretest – posttest non-randomized control group design.

Intact class (non-randomized groups) was assigned to two different technique or strategy of assessment - the treatment group (peer assessment) and control group (traditional assessment). In the experiment, the researcher is matching peer assessment group (treatment) with traditional assessment group (control); and further looking at the efficacy of peer assessment on achievement and interest. This design is represented as follows:

O₁ represents pretest scores for experiment and control groups

O₂ represents posttest scores for experiment and control groups

X₁ represents peer assessment

X₂ represents control

Area of Study

The area covered by this study is Enugu North Education Zone of Enugu State. The state is located in the South-Eastern part of Nigeria while the education zone is bounded in the North by Nsukka, East by Benue state, and South by Nkalagu in Ebonyi state. The land mass is approximately 7,162km². The choice of Enugu North Education Zone is based on the fact that it has sufficient number of schools in the urban areas where students can easily practice peer assessment with the teachers, also due to poor performance of students in Mathematics.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of all the Upper Basic II (UBII) students in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State numbering 5,628 (male = 2,492 and female =3,136) (Source; Statistics Unit PPSMB, Enugu State, 2022).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sampling technique adopted for the study was simple random sampling technique. Within Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State, there are nine schools altogether. Out of these nine schools, the researcher purposively selected five co-educational schools because objective (iii), (iv) and (v) of the study were gender related (i.e. both male and female). The names of the five co-educational schools were written on a piece of paper, placed in a box, shuffled and two of the schools randomly picked out, which has not exceeded 10% of the entire population within the study area.

After two co-educational secondary schools from Enugu North Local Government Area were randomly selected, a sample of 120 Upper Basic II (UB II) students (58 males and 62 females) was used for the study. One school would form the experimental group (which consisted of 30 males and 30 females) while one school would form the control group (which consisted of 28 males and 32 females). In each school one intact class was used and all the students in the intact class will be used for the study. The two schools that was used in this study were not close to each other. This is to avoid contamination of the experimental and control groups. Upper Basic II (UB II) Mathematics Students were used because Upper Basic I Students have not mastered the curriculum while the UB III students were too busy with the preparation of their Basic Certificate Examinations (BECE).

Instruments for Data Collection

Two instruments were used in the study for data collection. The instruments for data collection included Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS). The Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS) Questionnaire developed by the researcher, was on student's interest in Mathematics, Mensuration topic to be precise. The Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS) Questionnaire was a 5-item Yes/No questionnaire instrument to ascertain using mean and standard deviation which assessment method increased interest and academic achievement in Mathematics especially Mensuration. The Mathematics Achievement test was developed by the researcher and it is a 20-item instrument developed by the researcher based on the following list of topic contents; Angles in a Polygon, Angel of Elevation and Depression, and Bearing. MAT is an objective test with four answer options ranging from A to D, one (1) mark for one correct answer and zero (0) for wrong answer.

Validation of the Instruments

The instruments for this study were face and content validated. For face validation, the instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts in the Department of Science and Computer Education, two from Measurement and Evaluation unit, and one from Mathematics Education, Godfrey Okoye University, Enugu. The experts were asked to scrutinize the relevance of the items of the instruments to the study and the clarity of the items of the instruments. All comments and recommendations made by the experts were carefully incorporated into the final draft of the instruments. For content validation, a table of specification was constructed by the researcher. The relevant grammatical corrections were made on the MIS instrument, while the table of specification was used to ensure content validity of the MAT. It was to ensure that the status of the MAT covered all the content areas used in the study. It also guided the researcher to ensure that the items were evenly spread across the various levels of cognitive domain.

Reliability of the Instrument

The test and re-test method of ascertaining consistency over time was applied. Copies of the Mathematics Achievement Test were administered to 20 Upper Basic II students who did not take part in the final study. The

tests were administered again after two weeks. This procedure is appropriate for the pre-test post-test nature of this study. Computation of the Pearson Product Moment correlation between the two sets of scores yielded a coefficient of 0.81 for the reliability which the researcher considered adequate for the study.

Experimental Procedure:

Before the on-set of treatment, all the 120 Mathematics students involved in this study were administered with Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS) as pre-test. A total of three (3) lesson periods of 40 minutes duration each was taught to cover some concepts namely: Angles in a Polygon, Angel of Elevation and Depression, and Bearing. After the pretest, the mathematics tutors or teachers will be assigned to take over the teaching in their respective schools as they have been guided by the researcher.

The experimental group were guided by one Mathematics instructor; the mathematics teacher of the school who holds Bachelor's Degree in Mathematics Education. The package for the experiment is the Peer Assessment Technique (PAT) Package. The lessons are pre-prepared in a printed form.

The teacher taught the students, after which they were assessed using peer assessment technique where the students after receiving the lessons were asked to exchange their answer scripts with their neighbors (peers). They were to assess their peers using a marking guide which was prepared by the researcher. This technique of assessment is called Peer Assessment Technique.

Peer assessment is a technique of assessment whereby students are allowed to assess and grade their peers or classmates based on some benchmarks or guide provided by the teacher. This type of assessment is not widely used but it is very beneficial. It helps save time as well as makes the students sit up and improve their academic performance or achievement in the subject. The assistant (teacher) was instructed on how to use the PAT in assessing the students.

For the control group, the regular mathematics teacher also taught the students with the lesson note but assessed them with a different method. The teacher used the traditional assessment method which is the general method of assessment (teacher assessment) to assess the students after the completion of the lessons. By using this method, students submitted their answer scripts to the teacher; they are being assessed and graded by the teacher according to their performance. The experiment lasted for the same period of weeks.

Control of Extraneous Variable

The following procedures were adopted by the researcher to control some extraneous variables that might introduce bias into the study if they are not checked.

Novelty Effect: Novelty effect often occurs when students are working on a new material under a new teacher. The presence of a new teacher is likely to present a novelty effect on the students as a new teacher with a new method. To avoid this teacher bias, the students were taught by their regular mathematics teachers who had taken part in the training session organized by the researcher. In view of this arrangement, the researcher was not involved in the administration of the experiments.

Teacher Factor: No two individuals are exactly the same in skill and method. In order to control the errors that may surface due to differences among teachers, the researcher organized a uniform training programme for the teachers that were involved in the experiment. The objective of the training was to enable the teachers to acquire the competencies for carrying out the research conditions. The content of the training programme encompasses a proper knowledge of the content/subject matter, performance objectives and students' activities with regard to the assessment. The researcher was in close contact with the teachers during the period of experiment and discussion on the lesson plans and various students' activities with a view to ensuring that the teachers implement what they learned from the training.

By using the time tables of the school involved in the study, the researcher monitored the classes regularly to make sure that a uniform procedure of instruction is strictly adhered to all the teachers concerned. More so, all the four (4) teachers involved hold at least a Diploma in Mathematics.

Test Effect: To control the continuous testing effect, the researcher administered the pre-test and posttest at different lesson days. In this way, there was no disruption of the normal academic programmes.

Instructional Situation Variable: In order to ensure that the instructional situation was the same for the two schools selected for the study, the researcher issued out instructional guides to the regular Mathematics teachers (research assistant) in sampled schools for both experimental group A and control group B. Also teaching and testing was conducted in all the classes of Upper Basic II in the various schools selected for the study and not just in the intact classes drawn. This was done so as to avoid Hawthorne effect (a situation which research subject's behaviour is affected not by the treatment on its own but by their knowledge of participation in a study). After that, data from the target classes from both experimental and control group were used and others discarded.

Inter Group Variable: To eliminate the error of none randomization of the subjects, data from the study was analyzed using the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Subject Interaction: To avoid any possible interaction that may arise (inter-class discussion) between the two experimental groups, the researcher made sure that the experimental groups were drawn from different schools far from each other.

Method of Data Collection

The instrument for data collection in this study included Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS). The Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS) Questionnaire developed by the researcher, was on

student's interest in Mathematics. The Mathematics Interest Scale (MIS) Questionnaire was a 5-item Yes/No questionnaire instrument to ascertain using mean and standard deviation which assessment method increased academic achievement in Mathematics especially Mensuration. Mathematics Achievement Test was administered to the students before treatment began as pretests. Students' scores in the pre-tests should show their initial standing before treatment. At the end of treatment period, the items of this instrument was re-arranged and produced in a different color of paper so as not to make the students test wise and re-administered to the students as post-test. The pretest scores served as covariates to the post-test scores.

Method of Data Analysis

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha levels using the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). ANCOVA is deemed appropriate here because it served as a procedure for controlling the initial differences across groups as well as increasing the precision due to the extraneous variables thus reducing error variance. The test items were scored according to the predetermined marking guide.

Decision Rule;

The following rules were applied;

If the significant F of the SPSS used is less than 0.05 level set for this study, do not reject the null hypotheses, and otherwise reject.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Mensuration as a topic in Mathematics using peer assessment methods in the experimental group and the control group in both pretest and posttest?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Achievement Scores of Experimental and Control group in pretest and posttest.

Group	N	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D
Experimental group (peer assessment)	62	31.3	14.6	77.5	15.6
Control group	58	32.2	16.4	39.2	16.9

In Table 1, pretest mean score is 31.3 and post-test mean score is 77.5 for the students taught with peer assessment as against pretest mean score of 32.2 and post-test mean score of 39.2 for the students in the control group. Therefore peer assessment enhanced students' academic achievement in Mathematics more than the teacher assessment method.

Research Question 2

What are the mean interest scores of students taught Mensuration as a topic in Mathematics using peer assessment methods in the experimental group and the control group in both pretest and posttest?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Interest Scores of Experimental and Control group in pretest and posttest.

Group	N	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D
Experimental group (peer assessment)	64	33.3	16.4	79.7	17.4
Control group	56	34.2	18.2	37.4	18.7

In Table 2, pretest mean interest score is 33.3 and post-test interest mean score is 79.7 for the students taught with peer assessment as against pretest interest mean score of 34.2 and post-test interest mean score of 37.4 for the students in the control group. Therefore peer assessment enhanced students’ interest hence student’s academic achievement in Mathematics increased more with peer assessment than the teacher assessment method.

Null Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement of the pretest and posttest test scores of students in the peer assessment group (experimental group) and control group in Enugu Education Zone in Enugu State.

Table 6: ANCOVA on the mean achievement scores of upper basic two secondary schools students after being taught with peer assessment and teacher assessment method.

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	Cal. F	Crit. F	P ≥ 0.05
Pre-test scores	301.50	1	301.50	2.32		
Treatments models	9241.24	1	9241.24	71.03	5.22	Significant
Error	15221.83	117	130.101			
Corrected	24886.67	119				

In Table 6, it was observed that at 0.05 levels of significance, the calculated F (71.03) is greater than the critical F (5.22). Therefore, peer assessment method is significant in enhancing students’ academic achievement in mathematics.

Null Hypothesis 2

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in mean interest of the pretest and posttest test scores of students in the peer assessment group (experimental group) and control group in Enugu Education Zone in Enugu State.

Table 7: ANCOVA on the mean interest scores of upper basic two secondary schools students after being taught with peer assessment and teacher assessment method.

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	Cal. F	Crit. F	P ≥ 0.05
Pre-test scores	303.50	1	301.50	2.52		
Treatments models	11461.24	1	11461.24	73.03	7.22	Significant
Error	17443.83	119	152.101			
Corrected	26888.89	231				

In Table 7, it was observed that at 0.05 levels of significance, the calculated F (73.03) is greater than the critical F (7.22). Therefore, peer assessment method is significant in enhancing students' interest in mathematics.

Discussion of Findings

Effect of Peer Assessment on Academic Achievement

The findings revealed that students exposed to the peer assessment technique in mathematics performed significantly better than those assessed using traditional methods. This improvement can be attributed to the collaborative nature of peer assessment, which facilitates a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. Peer assessment encourages students to reflect on their work and that of their peers, providing immediate feedback that enhances their learning outcomes.

This aligns with Race (2011), who stated that peer assessment promotes deep learning, leading to improved academic achievement. Similarly, Biehler and Snowman (2017) emphasized that increased interest and motivation among students enhance concentration, commitment, and performance. Ezendu (2015) highlighted that motivational factors and learning approaches significantly influence academic outcomes, further supporting the study's findings.

The ANCOVA results showed a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students in the peer assessment and traditional assessment groups, confirming the efficacy of peer assessment in enhancing academic performance. This conclusion aligns with Juwaah (2013) and Sadler and Good (2016), who reported that peer assessment saves teachers' time while improving students' comprehension of course materials.

Effect of Peer Assessment on Interest in Mathematics

The study demonstrated that students taught using peer assessment exhibited significantly higher interest levels compared to those in the traditional assessment group. The hands-on, interactive nature of peer assessment fosters engagement, making learning more enjoyable and relatable for students. This higher interest level subsequently contributes to better academic achievement, as motivated students tend to focus more and perform better.

This finding is consistent with Biehler and Snowman (2017), who noted that interest is a critical factor in academic success. Peer assessment's emphasis on collaboration and student-centered learning aligns with constructivist principles, which advocate for active participation and critical thinking. Atanda and Jaiyeoba (2018) concluded

that improved methods, such as peer assessment, positively affect students' attitudes and achievements in mathematics.

The absence of significant gender differences in interest scores further highlights peer assessment's inclusivity and effectiveness across diverse groups. Hanrahan and Isaacs (2011) observed similar results, concluding that better teaching and assessment methods diminish gender disparities in academic performance.

Educational Implications of the Study

The findings of this study have implications to both students and teachers. Peer assessment can significantly improve the interest and academic achievements of mathematics students' comparison to the other assessment method of teaching mathematics which might not give any opportunity to learners to assess their own performance or the ones of their peers. This matter can guarantee both the learning of the students and increasing their motivation which is by itself an important factor in learning too.

Students on the other hand can tap from the findings of this study, when peer assessment is used, learners can also get more and more accurate in rating as any expert rater does after enough training and practice is offered.

Conclusion

This study examined the effects of peer assessment on students' academic achievement and interest in mensuration in upper basic schools in Enugu North Local Government Area. The findings revealed that peer assessment significantly improved both the achievement and interest levels of students in mathematics compared to traditional assessment methods.

The study demonstrated that peer assessment promotes active learning, collaboration, and critical thinking, enabling students to better understand and apply mathematical concepts. It also highlighted the inclusivity of peer assessment, as it proved effective across gender groups, ensuring equitable learning opportunities.

By fostering deeper engagement and motivation, peer assessment addresses the shortcomings of traditional methods and provides a viable alternative for enhancing students' learning experiences. These findings align with the constructivist theory, which advocates active participation and reflection as key components of effective learning.

In conclusion, the implementation of peer assessment in mathematics education holds significant potential for improving academic outcomes and sustaining student interest. Its adoption can contribute to better performance in both internal and external assessments, equipping students with the skills and confidence needed to succeed in mathematics and beyond.

Recommendations

In the light of findings from this study, the following recommendations were being made:

1. Peer-Assessment Strategy should be used by teachers in the assessment of students in Mathematics subject.

2. All stakeholders in the Education sector need to enforce the encouragement of teachers to have additional/ higher qualifications in Education, so that they will be exposed to different methods of assessment which always help to improve the academic performance of the students.
3. The parents and students should be made aware of the fact that there is no gender influence on students' academic performance; when they have been introduced to effective methods of assessment that will make them understand the contents of the subjects taught, they will excel in their academic achievements.

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